

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

The effect of NaOH and KOH on the strength-mechanical properties of alkali-activated composites based on granulated blast-furnace slag

To cite this article: R Gandel *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2792** 012001

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Attenuation characteristics of coda wave in Northern Aceh, Sumatra, Indonesia](#)
T Anggono, S Syuhada, B Pranata et al.
- [Research on new distributed distribution network hidden fault remote automatic recovery technology](#)
Lingyu Liang, Huanming Zhang, Xiangyu Zhao et al.
- [Temporal Estimators of Peculiar GRBs](#)
N. Noriega, E. F. Cárdenas, J. A. Chacón et al.

ECS The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

ECS UNITED

247th ECS Meeting
Montréal, Canada
May 18-22, 2025
Palais des Congrès de Montréal

Showcase your science!

Abstracts due December 6th

The effect of NaOH and KOH on the strength-mechanical properties of alkali-activated composites based on granulated blast-furnace slag

R Gandel¹, J Jeřábek¹, Z Marcalíková¹, P Čmiel²

¹VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Ludvíka Poděště 1875/17, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

²TESTSTAV, spol. s r.o., Františka Lýska 1599/6, 700 30 Ostrava – Bělský Les, Czech Republic

E-mail: radoslav.gandel@vsb.cz

Abstract. Alkali-activated systems are a more sustainable alternative to Portland cement concrete. The activation of latently hydraulic and pozzolanic raw materials in these composites is one of the many investigated factors, where the price ratio and the ability to optimally activate the mentioned precursors with the given activator play a major role. The subject of the presented work is a comparison of the influence of NaOH and KOH on the development of the strength-mechanical properties of alkali-activated materials based on granulated blast furnace slag - the secondary raw material of metallurgical processes.

1. Introduction

Constant technological progress, together with the idea of sustainable development and the principle of the circular economy, places demands on the increasingly frequent use of alternative raw materials and technological procedures in every area of industrial production. The construction industry is no exception, which, along with cement production, is one of the biggest contributors to global CO₂ emissions [1]. And replacing cement with an adequate raw material with a minimal impact on the environment and at the same time with a raw material that achieves the required strength-mechanical and durability properties in the given composite is the primary area of many researches. The majority of suitable materials are represented by the so-called latent hydraulic and pozzolanic admixtures, arising from other industrial processes as a by-product. The increase in demand for these materials categorized them from original waste raw materials to secondary raw materials, which affected the final price of the resulting composite. Granulated blast furnace slag is one of these materials.

Alkaline activation of granulated blast furnace slag proceeds similarly to cement. The presence of alkali causes the formation of alkaline silicates in the water, which participate in the dissolution of the glass phase. Alkaline ions initially trigger the reaction, and after condensation and crystallization processes, they further participate in the formation of the hydration gel. The most commonly used alkaline activators are alkali metal compounds such as silicates, carbonates and hydroxides (especially potassium and sodium) in powder or liquid form. Alkaline activation depends not only on the specific surface and chemical composition of the granulated blast furnace slag, technological procedures and other factors, but also on the type and concentration of the alkaline activator. In general, potassium activators can be considered the most suitable, which support the formation of a hydration gel and a

stronger structure, thereby achieving better strength characteristics. The disadvantage remains their higher purchase price. On the other hand, although sodium activators dissolve the glass phase well and the purchase price is lower than potassium activators, they do not reach the strength characteristics of alkali-activated composites based on slag activated by potassium activators. As the content of alkaline activator increases, the strength of the composite increases to a certain extent, after which the strength decreases drastically. This causes increased hydration heat, which has an impact on the formation of unwanted microcracks. In addition, it can increase the possibility of an alkaline-silica reaction of the aggregate [2-4].

The grinding fineness of granulated blast furnace slag is slightly higher compared to Portland cement and, together with the necessary lower water coefficient, favorably affects the workability and rheological properties of the fresh mixture (which is the reason for its use in self-compacting concrete) and the porosity of the resulting composite. Previous researches [5, 6] proved that even in alkali-activated composites with slag binder, it is possible to achieve strength characteristics equal to and better than those of traditional concrete with Portland cement. In addition, due to the lower content of calcium hydroxide and lower porosity, alkali-activated materials based on blast furnace slag acquire better chemical resistance, especially against sulfates. The mentioned properties therefore qualify blast furnace slag as a suitable precursor for alkaline activated materials [7-9]. In addition, it is necessary to monitor a number of other properties, such as the effect of extreme temperatures, whether low, in the form of a frost resistance test [10] or exposure to high temperatures in a furnace [11]. In recent years, research has also focused on the linking of alkali-activated materials with other materials, such as waste materials from construction activities [12] or in the form of hybrid materials, for example with fiber reinforced concrete [13].

When designing the mixture of alkaline activated systems, it is necessary to find a balance between the required strength characteristics, workability, durability and economic efficiency. One of the most widely used alkaline activators for systems based on granulated blast furnace slag is, for financial reasons, sodium hydroxide or in combination with a water glass. Despite the lower strength characteristics compared to KOH-activated systems, it is possible to use NaOH in mixtures with a lower water ratio, in addition, NaOH ions are smaller compared to KOH ions and accelerate the activation of blast furnace slag and the dissolution of its silicate components, which can result in a faster onset of initial strength. Another admixture of alkali-activated slag materials is usually some pozzolanic material, such as fly ash, metakaolin or silica fume. Most often, blast furnace slag is used in combination with power plant ash, which is the most affordable of the mentioned admixtures. The grains of power plant fly ash are smaller compared to granulated blast furnace slag, which leads to a denser structure of the resulting composite in the case of its use in alkali-activated materials and thus to improved strength and durability. In the case of alkali-activated materials based on slag-ash binder, the slag content can reach a wide range, but according to some researches [14], the recommended effective dose of slag in alkali-activated slag-ash composites is up to 70% [15].

2. Results of the experimental program

The mentioned experimental program deals with monitoring the effect of alkaline activators NaOH and KOH on the strength-mechanical parameters of slag-based composites. The observed properties were tested on two mixtures, with the only variation in the type of alkaline activator. The raw materials used and their dosage are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Composition of tested mixtures

Input materials	weight [kg] per 1 m ³
blast furnace slag JMŠ 420	450
sodium silicate, Ms = 2,0	56.3
water	172
plasticizer Chrysoplast 760	9
aggregate 0-4 mm, Tovačov	920
aggregate 4-8 mm, Litice	670
NaOH/KOH solution	42

The influence of the choice of alkaline activator on the compressive strength, tensile splitting strength, flexural strength and dynamic modulus of elasticity was monitored. The set of samples contained beams with dimensions of 40x40x160 mm, which were tested for the speed of propagation of ultrasonic waves, flexural strength and compressive strength in a time range of 2-56 days. In addition, the 100 mm cube samples were tested for standard 28-day compressive strength and the 150 mm cube samples for 28-day tensile splitting strength. The presented results are part of a larger experimental program dealing with a number of other characteristics and properties of alkali-activated composites.

The dynamic modulus of elasticity was derived from the results of the propagation speed of ultrasonic waves measured by the ultrasonic pulse method based on the *ČSN 73 1371 Non-destructive testing of concrete – Method of ultrasonic pulse testing of concrete* [16] standard, before the flexural strength test. In each series, 3 beams with dimensions of 40x40x160 mm were tested, in the time range of 2-56 days. The results are shown in the graph in figure 1.

Figure 1. Development of dynamic modulus of elasticity

In the case of NaOH mixture, the samples were damaged during demolding due to their insufficient handling strength, and therefore further tests could not be performed. The samples with the KOH mixture already reached a relatively constant value of the dynamic modulus of elasticity after 14 days, approximately 41 GPa, with a slight increase after 56 days to 43.5 GPa and a small dispersion of the

values (coefficient of variation was 2.51%). Samples with the NaOH mixture began to approach this limit after 21 days; the subsequent increase in the dynamic modulus of elasticity was negligible (after 56 days it reached the value of 41.1 GPa with the variation coefficient of 1.15%). In the case of one sample of the KOH formula after 7 days, higher ultrasonic wave propagation velocities occurred compared to the remaining samples of this series, which affected the standard deviation of the entire statistical set.

Other characteristics tested were flexural strength and compressive strength, performed on the beams on which the speed of propagation of ultrasonic waves was originally measured. Both strength characteristics were evaluated in accordance with standard *ČSN EN 196-1 Methods of testing cement - Part 1: Determination of strength* [17]. The following figures 2 and 3 represent their graphical representation.

Figure 2. Development of flexural strength

Figure 3. Development of compressive strength

From the flexural strengths results in the graph in figure 2, slightly higher values are more noticeable for samples from the KOH mixture, but after 28 days the samples from the NaOH mixture reached almost the same flexural strength - approximately 6.6 MPa, with a coefficient of variation of 3.22% for the NaOH mixture and 0.27% for the KOH mixture. After 56 days, one of the samples of the KOH mixture had an outlier in flexural strength, which adversely affected the statistical dataset. Nevertheless, at this time both mixtures reached approximate values of flexural strength 7 ± 1 MPa.

The graph in figure. 3 shows more obvious differences in compressive strength between the given mixtures. After the standard 28 days, the compressive strength of the KOH mixture reached 62 MPa (coefficient of variation – 3.74%), the NaOH mixture reached about 25% lower - 46 MPa (coefficient of variation – 7.19%). After 56 days, only a slight increase in the compressive strength (with a higher dispersion of values – coefficient of variation reached 13.36%) was recorded for the these samples - compared to 28 days, it rose to 48 MPa. In the case of samples of the KOH mixture, the compressive strength after 56 days increased by 9 MPa (with coefficient of variation 4.27%) compared to the standard strength.

In figure 4 it is possible to see the cross-sectional area of the samples of mixtures with NaOH (left) and KOH (right) colored green after 7 days. It is interesting that the samples with NaOH activator were not stained to a depth of approx. 5 mm, which together with the low initial strengths may indicate a

slower reaction of the slag with the alkaline activator. In this case, however, it is hasty to draw conclusions without a more detailed chemical analysis, which was not the part of this experiment.

Figure 4. Detail of the samples of NaOH mixture (left) and KOH mixture (right) after the flexural strength test after 7 days

Table 2 summarizes the standard 28-day tensile splitting strengths (performed on three 150 mm edge length cubes, due to standard *ČSN EN 12390-6. Testing hardened concrete - Part 6: Tensile splitting strength of test specimens* [18]) with corresponding variability characteristics. The tensile splitting strength of NaOH samples was approximately 15% lower than that of KOH samples.

Table 2. Standard 28-day tensile splitting strengths

Mixture	Tensile splitting strength [MPa]	Unbiased sample standard deviation [MPa]	Coefficient of variation [%]
NaOH	3.41	0.20	5.86
KOH	3.95	0.13	3.29

The graph in the figure 5 compares the different 28-day compressive strength of both mixtures made on beams 40x40x160 mm (3 samples), with an effective area of 1600 mm², and cubes with an edge length of 100 mm (3 samples). Tests of cube samples were performed according to the standard *ČSN EN 12390-3. Testing hardened concrete – Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens* [19]. In both cases, the compressive strengths of the beams were about 5% higher than the cube strengths. Larger standard deviations from the average strength are also evident in the case of samples of the NaOH mixture.

Figure 5. Comparison of 28-day compressive strength on samples of beams with dimension of 40x40x160 mm and cubes with 100 mm edge

3. Conclusion

The following can be concluded from the results of the presented experimental program [20]:

- The increase in the initial strength of the alkali-activated composite (hereinafter AAC) with the NaOH activator did not even reach the minimum handling strength after 2 days, the samples disintegrated immediately after demoulding, so further test attempts were excluded.
- The dynamic modulus of elasticity had a steady increase during the test period for both AAC mixtures. After 56 days, both mixtures reached approximately similar values - NaOH mixture 41 GPa, KOH 43.5 GPa.
- The compressive strength of the AAC mixture with NaOH increased only slightly after 28 days. After 56 days, it reached a value of 48 MPa. An increase in compressive strength was noted for the AAC mixture with KOH during the entire test period. After 56 days, samples of the KOH mixture reached a compressive strength of 71 MPa, which is approximately a 15% increase over its standard (28-day) strength and 48% more than the 56-day strength of the NaOH mixture. Its further growth over time is also expected.
- Flexural strength increased moderately after 21 days for both mixtures. After 56 days, the strength values were approximately the same, namely 7 ± 0.1 MPa.
- After standard 28 days, the tensile splitting strength of the AAC with KOH was approximately 15% greater than the tensile splitting strength of the mixture with NaOH.
- Overall, the strength-mechanical properties of the AAC mixture with KOH reached more favourable values than the AAC with NaOH; due to the higher purchase price of the KOH activator, it is necessary to assess the use of selected composites for each application individually.

References

- [1] 2021 Concrete needs to lose its colossal carbon footprint *Nature* **597** 593-594
- [2] Hajzler J, Bílek V, Kotrla J and Kucharčzyková B 2022 Influence of activator type and slag volume fraction on properties of alkali-activated slag pastes *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **2341** 012013
- [3] Marvila M T, Azevedo A R G, Matos P R, Monteiro S N and Vieira C M F 2021 Rheological and

- the Fresh State Properties of Alkali-Activated Mortars by Blast Furnace Slag *Materials* **14** 2069
- [4] Miyazawa Y, Sugiyama H and Yokomuro T 2017 Effect of specific surface area of ground granulated blast furnace slag and its substitution rate on strength development of concrete *Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering* **82** 1517-1526
- [5] Rossi L, Patel R A and Dehn F 2023 Compressive behaviour of alkali-activated slag-based concrete and Portland cement concrete incorporating novel multiple hooked-end steel fibres *Mater Struct* **56** 96
- [6] Mohamed O A 2019 A Review of Durability and Strength Characteristics of Alkali-Activated Slag Concrete *Materials* **12** 1198
- [7] Fu Q, Bu M, Zhang Z, Xu W, Yuan Q, Niu D 2023 Hydration Characteristics and Microstructure of Alkali-Activated Slag Concrete: A Review *Engineering* **20** 162-179
- [8] Dinakar, P, Sethy K, Sahoo 2013 Design of Self-Compacting Concrete with Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag *Materials & Design* **43** 161-169
- [9] Murat D, Mehmet K, Mehrzad M, Sulfate resistance of alkali-activated slag/Portland cement mortar produced with lightweight pumice aggregate 2021 *Construction and Building Materials* **304** 124671
- [10] Bilek V, Sucharda O, Bujdos D, Frost Resistance of Alkali-Activated Concrete—An Important Pillar of Their Sustainability 2021 *Sustainability* 13 473
- [11] Nemeč J, Gandel R, Jerabek J, Sucharda O, Bilek V, Properties of Selected Alkali-activated Materials for Sustainable development 2024 *Civil and Environmental Engineering* 20 (1)
- [12] Robayo-Salazar R A, Rivera J F, de Gutiérrez R M, Alkali-activated building materials made with recycled construction and demolition wastes, 2017 *Construction and Building Materials* 149 130-138
- [13] Gandel R, Jerabek J, Marcalikova Z, Reinforced Concrete Beams Without Shear Reinforcement Using Fiber Reinforced Concrete and Alkali-Activated Material 2023 *Civil and Environmental Engineering* 19 (1) 348–56
- [14] Mohamed O A, Al Khattab R, Al Hawat W, Effect of relative GGBS/fly contents and alkaline solution concentration on compressive strength development of geopolymers subjected to sulfuric acid 2022 *Scientific Reports* **12** 5634.....10
- [15] Provis J L 2018 Alkali-activated materials *Cement and Concrete Research* **114** 40-48
- [16] ČSN 73 1371 Non-destructive testing of concrete – Method of ultrasonic pulse testing of concrete. Praha: The Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, 2011
- [17] ČSN EN 196-1 Methods of testing cement - Part 1: Determination of strength. Prague: The Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, 2016
- [18] ČSN EN 12390-6. Testing hardened concrete - Part 6: Tensile splitting strength of test specimens. Prague: The Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, 2024
- [19] ČSN EN 12390-3. Testing hardened concrete – Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens. Prague: The Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, 2020
- [20] Experimental dataset DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10777097

Acknowledgments

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic.